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**A SCRIPTURE-BASED,
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Sola Scriptura in Nigerian Pentecostal Theology: Continuity and Divergence from Classical Reformation Theology

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Abstract

Sola scriptura is a doctrine that affirms that the scripture alone is the supreme authority in matters of faith and practices. The doctrine of *sola scriptura* stands as a foundational principle of the Protestant Reformation. From the memory lane, within the sixteenth-century European ecclesia context, *sola scriptura* has been received, reinterpreted, and sometimes contested in contemporary Christianity. The thrust of this paper, therefore, is to examine how *sola scriptura* is understood and practiced within Nigerian Pentecostal theology. The paper argues that Nigerian Pentecostalism demonstrates both continuity with classical reformation theology through its high regard for the Bible and significant divergence through its strong emphasis on prophetic revelation, charismatic experience, and authoritative leadership. The paper adopts a historical-theological and contextual approach to unearth the historical roots of *sola scriptura*, outlining its classical Reformation meaning and dissecting its reinterpretation within Nigerian Pentecostal movements. The paper concludes by suggesting a formative structure for rearticulating *sola scriptura* in Nigerian Pentecostal theology in a way that affirms scripture's competency while critically engaging charismatic experience.

Keywords: *sola scriptura, nigerian pentecostalism, biblical hermeneutics, reformation theology, prophetic revelation*

Introduction

Sola scriptura, a Latin phrase that means “scripture alone,” is a theological doctrine that asserts that the Bible alone is the authoritative source of religious truth and practice. It highlights the belief that the scriptures are sufficient for direction and understanding God’s will and guidance for life. The doctrine of *sola scriptura* remains one of the most defining principles of Protestant identity. As a Reformation doctrine, it asserted the primacy of the scripture over Church traditions and magisterial authority, claiming that the scripture alone is the final norm for Christian beliefs and conduct.¹ In contemporary Christianity, the meaning and application of *sola scriptura* are far from uniform. In other words, *sola scriptura* is neither uniformly interpreted nor constantly applied. Pentecostalism presents a compelling case for examining how this doctrine is appropriated, adapted, or functionally modified in new contexts.

Nigerian Pentecostalism has emerged as one of the most influential expressions of Christianity, characterized by vibrant worship, prophetic utterances, healing ministries, and charismatic leadership. Nigerian Pentecostal churches simultaneously affirm a strong commitment to the Bible as the word of God.² Yet the prominence of prophecy, visions, dreams, and spiritual direction raises critical theological questions about authority and revelation.

The study investigates the theological relationship between *sola scriptura* and Nigerian Pentecostal theology. Some million-dollar questions that are germane to this study are how is *sola scriptura* understood in classical reformation theology? How do Nigerian Pentecostal churches articulate and practice scriptural authority? To what extent does Nigerian Pentecostalism demonstrate continuity and divergence from classical Reformation formulations of *sola scriptura*?

The argument of this study is that Nigerian Pentecostal theology reflects a functional modification of *sola scriptura*. While affirming the scripture as authoritative in principle, Pentecostal praxis often places charismatic revelation alongside or at times above the scripture practice. This tension raises significant questions for biblical interpretation, ecclesial authority, and prophetic ethics in the Nigerian context.

¹ Alister E. McGrath, *Reformation Thought: An Introduction*, 4th edition. (Oxford: Wiley Blackwell, 2012), 92-95.

² Ruth Marshall, *Political Spiritualities: The Pentecostal Revolution in Nigeria*. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2009), 15

1.1 Scriptural Review

Sola scriptura is a Reformation doctrine that postulates that the scripture has the supreme authority on Christian faith and practices. In other words, Christian faith and practices are primarily embedded in the biblical witness itself. Both classical Reformation theology and Nigerian Pentecostal theology appeal to scripture to justify theological authority, though they differ in interpretive orientation and ecclesial application.

This section examines the major biblical texts that serve as the foundation for the doctrine of *sola scriptura* and evaluates their appropriation within Nigerian Pentecostal theology in comparison with classical Reformation formulations.

1.1.1 Scripture as the Supreme Rule of Divine Revelation

A significant scriptural foundation for *sola scriptura* is 2 Tim. 3:16-17, which states that “All scripture is given by the inspiration of God (*theopneustos*: God breathed) and is profitable for teaching, reproof, correction, and training in righteousness.³ The assertion that scripture is inspired affirms its divine origin and character and implies something rather stronger than the word “inspiration.” More accurately, one can say the scriptures are breathed out by God. The interpretation given by the Reformation theologian on this passage is that both the divine origin and the functional sufficiency of scripture are for the total life of faith.

Nigerian Pentecostal theology also agrees that this scripture passage depicts evidence of biblical inspiration and usefulness. However, scripture’s adequacy is often interpreted practically rather than normatively and lays emphasis on its effectiveness when activated through faith, prayers, or prophetic interpretation.

1.1.2 The Genuine Authority of Scripture

Classical *sola scriptura* maintains that the scripture’s authority and genuineness lie in being the word of God. The book of Isa. 8: 20 establishes scripture as the decisive standard for determining truth claims, while Psa. 19: 7 – 11 extols the perfection, reliability, and sufficiency of God’s law.⁴ As a matter of fact, Jesus himself repeatedly referred to the scripture as the final authority in theological disputes. Jesus declared that “Scripture cannot be broken” (Jn. 10: 35).⁵ In other words, Jesus was affirming that the authority of the Law cannot be annulled. Nigerian Pentecostal churches regularly engage this text in preaching and teaching, especially in defending biblical

³ See The Holy Bible, RSV, Timothy 3: 16 – 17

⁴ See The Holy Bible, RSV, Isaiah 8: 20; Psalms 19: 7 – 11.

⁵ See The Holy Bible, RSV, John 10: 35

morality against secular influences. Yet, interpretive authority is often mediated through charismatic leaders who claim special revelation or divine insight. In such a context, scripture's self-authenticating authority may be implicitly subordinated to prophetic interpretation, thereby reshaping the Reformation understanding of biblical finality.

1.1.3 Scripture and the Ministry of the Holy Spirit

Both the Reformation and the Pentecostal tradition agree on the indispensable role of the Holy Spirit in scripture interpretation. Texts such as Jn. 16: 13 and 1Cor. 2: 10 – 14 emphasize that the Holy Spirit enables spiritual understanding of the scripture rather than by human wisdom.⁶ In other words, true understanding of the scripture is not natural to us; it is God's gift through the Holy Spirit (Matt. 11:25; 16:17). The Reformers, however, carefully distinguished between illumination and revelation, insisting that the Holy Spirit enables believers to understand the scripture without adding new doctrinal content beyond the biblical canon.⁷ Nigerian Pentecostal theology often extends the role of the Holy Spirit beyond illumination to include revelatory experience justified by Acts 2:17–18, which speaks of dreams, visions, and prophecy in the last days.⁸

While the Reformers interpreted this passage within a redemptive-historical structure and tied it to the apostolic era, Pentecostals tend to read it as traditional for contemporary Christian experience. This divergence in interpretation has important implications for how *sola scriptura* is practiced in a Pentecostal context.

1.1.4 Scripture, Apostolic Teaching, and Communal Discernment

The New Testament agrees that the scripture is the yardstick for evaluating doctrinal claims. Acts 17:11 commends the Bereans for examining the scriptures daily to ascertain Paul's teaching, demonstrating that even the apostolic proclamation was also subject to scriptural scrutiny.⁹ This text buttressed the Reformation arguments against unchecked Church leaders' authority. In Nigerian Pentecostal settings, this passage is frequently cited but rarely applied. Church traditions, prophetic directives, and the teachings of the founders, or "men of God," often function as interpretive authorities that are not rigorously tested against scripture. Consequently, communal discernment may prioritize charismatic authority over careful biblical exegesis.

⁶ See The Holy Bible, NRSV, John 16: 13; Corinthians 2: 10 – 14

⁷ Martin Luther, *The Bondage of the Will* (Grand Rapids: Revell, 1957), 121-23

⁸ See The Holy Bible, RSV, Acts 2: 17 – 18, this text was a prophecy by Prophet Joel

⁹ See The Holy Bible, RSV, Acts 17: 11

1.1.5 Scriptural Warnings Against Extra-Biblical Authority

The biblical canon itself contains strong warnings against augmenting divine revelation. The book of Deuteronomy 4:2 cautions Israel not to add or subtract from God's commandments. While the book of Revelation 22: 28 – 19, issues severe warnings against interfering with prophetic revelations.¹⁰ Reformation theologians interpreted these texts as safeguarding the sufficiency and authority of the scripture. But the Pentecostal theology, though acknowledging these warnings, interpreted it as a prohibition against heretical teachings rather than against subtle expansion of authority through prophetic declarations, ritualized instructions, or personalized revelations. This selective application allows extra-biblical practices to coexist with professed commitment to *sola scriptura*.

1.2 The Classical Reformation Doctrine of Sola Scriptura

Sola scriptura emerged as a doctrine within the sixteenth-century Protestant Reformation. The doctrine was a response to the theological excesses of late medieval Catholicism. Martin Luther's insistence at the Diet of Worms in 1521 that his conscience was bound by the word of God alone epitomized this conviction.¹¹ Luther was of the opinion that the scripture has the highest authority because it witnesses about Christ and explicitly conveys the gospel. John Calvin further arranged the doctrine and described the scripture as the rule that governs all theological norms.¹² Calvin remarked that one of the important roles of the Holy Spirit is that He illuminates the biblical text for believers' understanding, but not as a source of new revelation independent of the scripture.

Therefore, *sola scriptura* did not deny the work of the Holy Spirit but subordinated all claims of revelation to the *logos* (written word). Thus, classical *sola scriptura* has some interconnected claims: first, the scripture alone possesses absolute authority. Second, the scripture is sufficient for *soteria* (salvation) and faithful living. Third, the scripture is explicit in essential matters. Lastly, no extrabiblical revelation may contradict the scripture.¹³ In sum, the Reformers did not reject the Church tradition totally but insisted that tradition must remain accountable to the scripture. In other words, tradition must align with the scripture.

1.3 Historical and Theological Context of Nigerian Pentecostalism

Nigerian Pentecostalism resulted from a complex interplay of indigenous religious movements, missionary Christianity influences, and later charismatic renewal. Its root can be traced to early

¹⁰ See The Holy Bible, RSV, Deuteronomy 4: 2; Revelation 22: 18 - 19

¹¹ Martin Luther, "Here I Stand," in Luther's Works, vol 32 (Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1971), 112-113

¹² John Calvin, Institutes of the Christian Religion, ed. John McNeill (Louisville: Westminster Press, 1960), 171

¹³ Louis Berkhof, Systematic Theology, (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans Publishers, 1958), 153- 160

twentieth-century indigenous Christian expressions that emphasized prayers, healing, and spiritual power as responses to the perceived inadequacies of mission Churches in addressing African existential concerns.¹⁴ The Aladura movements, such as the Cherubim and Seraphim and the Church of the Lord, played a foundational role in preparing the religious soil for Pentecostal spirituality in Nigeria to sprout. These movements stressed divine healing, prophecy, vision, and direct spiritual experience, thereby reshaping Christian practice within an African worldview.¹⁵ The formal introduction of classical Pentecostalism into Nigeria occurred through transnational missionary networks linked to the Azusa Street revival in 1906 and later through affiliations with American Pentecostal denominations such as the Assemblies of God.¹⁶ By the mid-twentieth century, Pentecostalism had gained significant support, particularly in Southwestern Nigeria, where it agreed with local cosmologies that emphasized spiritual causality, power encounters, and divine intervention.¹⁷

The late twentieth century witnessed the rise of neo-Pentecostal and Charismatic movements, often described as the third wave of Pentecostalism. Churches such as the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Deeper Life Bible Church, Living Faith Church (Winner Chapel), and Christ Embassy emerged as influential religious institutions with extensive national and transnational reach.¹⁸ These movements combined Pentecostal spirituality with modern organizational structures, mass media engagement, prosperity teaching, and charismatic leadership.¹⁹

1.4 Theological Orientation of Nigerian Pentecostalism

Theologically, Nigerian Pentecostalism is known for a strong emphasis on experiential faith, pneumatic immediacy, and the tangible manifestation of divine power. The core of the theological worldview of the Pentecostal is the conviction that the Holy Spirit intervenes in the affairs of man, addressing concrete issues such as poverty, illness, infertility, and spiritual oppression.²⁰

The scripture occupies a central place in Nigerian Pentecostal theology; the Bible is widely regarded as the inspired word of God and is frequently cited in preaching, prayers, and doctrinal

¹⁴ J. Pell, *Religious Encounter and the making of the Yoruba* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 2000), 278- 282

¹⁵ M. A. Ojo, *The End – Time Army: Charismatic Movements in Modern Nigeria*, (Trenton: Africa World Press, 2006), 29-34

¹⁶ Allan Anderson, *An Introduction to Pentecostalism: Global Charismatic Christianity* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2014),46-49

¹⁷ O. Kalu, *African Pentecostalism: An Introduction* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008), 83-88

¹⁸ Ruth Marshall, *Political Spiritualities: The Pentecostal Revolution in Nigeria*, (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2009), 37 - 42

¹⁹ Paul Gifford, *Christianity, Development, and Modernity in Africa* (London: Hurst, 2015), 91-97

²⁰ C. N. Omenyo, “Penticostalism and the African Culture,” *Exchange*, 40, no 2 (2011): 168 - 172

instructions.²¹ However, biblical interpretation often operates within a practical and devotional structure, privileging texts that promise healing, victory, prosperity, and divine protection. This interpretive approach represents a functional theology shaped by lived experience rather than systematic doctrinal reflection.²² A distinguishing theological quality of Nigerian Pentecostalism is its strong prophetic consciousness. Prophecy, visions, dreams, and words of knowledge are commonly understood as contemporary modes of divine communication. These charismatic expressions are often treated as authoritative guidance for personal and communal decision-making.²³ While such practices affirm belief in the ongoing work of the Holy Spirit, they also introduce tension concerning the relationship between the scripture and extra-biblical revelation.

1.5 Authority, Revelation, and Charismatic Leadership

Authority in Nigerian Pentecostalism is frequently mediated through charismatic leaders who are believed to be specially anointed vessels of divine revelation. Founders or general overseers often function as primary interpreters of the scripture and prophetic insight, exercising considerable influence over doctrine and practice.²⁴ This leadership pattern portrays both biblical models of prophetic authority and African cultural assumptions about spiritual mediation and hierarchy. Theologically, this has resulted in a dynamic but contested authority structure in which scripture, prophetic revelation, and pastoral charisma coexist.

While the *sola scriptura* is affirmed verbally by the Pentecostals, the practical authority of prophecy and spiritual direction can, at times, rival or overshadow the normative role of the scripture.²⁵ This development represents Pentecostals' contextual theological adaptation rather than a deliberate rejection of Protestant orthodoxy, yet it raises critical questions concerning doctrinal accountability, ecclesial authority, and ethical discernment.

1.6 Continuity with *Sola Scriptura* in Nigerian Pentecostal Theology

Despite the critiques concerning the emphasis on prophecy and charismatic experience by the Pentecostals, Pentecostal theology exhibits notable continuity with the classical Reformation doctrine of *sola scriptura*. At the doctrinal level, Nigerian Pentecostal churches consistently affirm the Bible as the inspired and authoritative word of God. Their doctrinal statement, sermon, and teaching manuals commonly give credence to the scripture as the final authority in the matter of

²¹ Allan Anderson, *African Reformation: African Initiated Christianity in the 20th Century*, (Trenton: African World Press, 2001), 215 - 218

²² Marshall, *Political Spiritualities*, 44- 46

²³ Ojo, *End – Time army* , 101- 106

²⁴ Gifford, *Christianity, Development, and Modernity*, 98-104

²⁵ Kenneth A. Mathison, *The Shape of Sola Scriptura*(Moscow: Canon Press, 2001), 237 – 240

faith and Christian living.²⁶ This position agrees closely with the Reformation insistence that scripture alone possesses ultimate normative authority over the Church. Pentecostal leaders frequently use biblical texts to back up their teachings, spiritual practices, and ethical instructions. Public preaching and private devotion are saturated with quotations from the scripture, reinforcing the perception that Pentecostal Christianity is fundamentally Bible-centered.²⁷ In this respect, Nigerian Pentecostalism agrees firmly with the Protestant tradition that originated from the Reformation's challenge to Church magisterial authority.

Another point of continuity with *sola scriptura* in Nigerian Pentecostalism is the rejection of church tradition as an independent source of doctrinal authority. Pentecostal churches generally resist appeals to creeds, councils, or historical tradition unless they are perceived to align clearly with the scripture.²⁸ This posture reveals the Reformers' critique of medieval Catholicism, which they believed elevated tradition to a level that undermined biblical authority.

Furthermore, Nigerian Pentecostal theology strongly encourages individual believers to read, memorize, confess, and apply the scripture personally. Bible reading plans, memory verses, and scriptural confession are central features of Pentecostal spirituality.²⁹ This emphasis agrees with the Reformation's insistence that all believers should have direct access to the biblical text. This insistence on personal Bible engagement also reflects the Reformation doctrine of the priesthood of all believers, even if this doctrine is not always explicitly articulated. The Bible is not reserved for clerical interpretation alone but presented as accessible and relevant to the everyday lives of believers.

Moreover, in the aspect of personal ethics, such as sexual ethics, honesty, discipline, and holiness, Nigerian Pentecostal churches always appeal to the scripture as the authoritative standard. Ethical exhortations are framed in explicitly biblical terms, often drawn from both Old and New Testament texts.³⁰ This ethical reliance on the scripture reflects a key dimension of *sola scriptura*, that is, the conviction that the Bible provides sufficient guidance for faithful Christian living.

Furthermore, evangelism and discipleship within Nigerian Pentecostalism are typically scripture-centered. Conversion narratives often emphasize hearing or encountering the word of God, and discipleship programs are structured around systematic Bible teachings.³¹ This emphasis

²⁶ Alister E. McGrath, *Reformation Thought: An Introduction*, 92-95

²⁷ Ruth Marshall, *Political Spiritualities*, 44- 46

²⁸ Kenneth A Mathison, *The Shape of Sola Scriptura*, 87 - 94

²⁹ Allan Anderson, *An Introduction to Pentecostalism*, 223- 230

³⁰ Cephas N Omenyo, "Pentecostalism and the African Culture," 170- 175

³¹ O Kalu, *African Pentecostalism*, 185- 190

underscores Pentecostalism's continuity with the Reformation belief that faith is acquired and sustained through the proclamation of the word of God (Rom. 10:17).

1.7 Divergence from *Sola Scriptura* in Nigerian Pentecostal Theology

While Nigerian Pentecostal theology affirms the authority of the scripture at the level of confession, significant divergences from the classical Reformation doctrine of *sola scriptura* emerge at the level of practice and theological methods. These divergences are most evident in the elevation of prophetic revelation, the authority of charismatic leaders, and practical hermeneutics.

A major point of divergence from *sola scriptura* lies in the prominent role accorded to prophetic revelation within Nigerian Pentecostalism. Prophecies, visions, dreams, and words of knowledge are commonly regarded as direct communication from God and are frequently treated as authoritative guidance for personal decisions and communal practices.³² In many Pentecostal settings, such revelations function with a level of authority that rivals scripture even when they lack explicit biblical foundation. Classical Reformation theology, though affirming the work of the Holy Spirit, rejects the notion of continuing doctrinal revelation that goes beyond the scripture.

Furthermore, for the Reformers, the Spirit's role was to illumine the biblical text rather than introduce new revelatory content.³³ The Pentecostal practice of treating prophetic utterances as binding instructions therefore represents a systemic alteration of the Reformation's understanding of revelation.

Another significant divergence concerns the concentration of theological authority in charismatic leaders. Founders and senior pastors in Nigerian Pentecostal churches often occupy positions of authority as interpreters of scripture and mediators of divine revelation. Their teachings and prophetic insight are rarely subjected to communal discernment or theological scrutiny.³⁴ The leadership pattern contrasts sharply with the Reformation emphasis on the priesthood of all believers and the accountability of church leaders to scripture and the wider Christian community. While the Reformers acknowledged the significance of pastoral leadership, they consistently rejected any authority that functioned independently of or above the scripture.³⁵ In practice, however, the Nigerian Pentecostal leadership structure approximates a quasi-magisterial authority, undermining the *sola scriptura* principle.

³² Matthew A Ojo, *The End – Time Army*, 98- 104

³³ John Calvin, *Institute of Christian Religion*, 191

³⁴ Paul Gifford, *Christianity, Development and Modernity*, 98- 104

³⁵ Martin Luther, *Luther Works*, vol. 32, (Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1971), 112- 115

Furthermore, another area of departure of Pentecostal theology from the classical Reformation is that the Nigerian Pentecostal interpretation of the scripture often adopts a pragmatic and outcome-oriented approach. Biblical texts are selected and interpreted based on their perceived ability to address immediate existential concerns such as healing, prosperity, protection, and success.³⁶ While this approach reflects genuine pastoral sensitivity, it often results in decontextualized readings that prioritize application over exegesis. Such hermeneutical practices diverge from the Reformers' commitment to grammatical-historical interpretation, which sought to recover the original meaning of biblical text within their literary and historical context.³⁷ The selective use of the scripture to validate prophetic claims or prosperity teachings further weakens the normative function of the scripture envisioned by *sola scriptura*.

1.8 Theological and Ethical Implications

The practical honouring of prophetic revelation as equal to the scripture raises serious questions about the authority and accountability of the scripture. The doctrine of *Sola Scriptura* is not merely a hermeneutical principle but a comprehensive theological framework with far-reaching ethical consequences. Within Christian theology, particularly in contexts such as Nigerian Pentecostalism, *sola scriptura* shapes understandings of revelation, authority, ecclesial accountability, moral discernment, and social responsibility.

1.8.1 Theological Implications of *Sola Scriptura*

Theologically, *sola scriptura* affirms scripture as the supreme and sufficient revelation of God's will for salvation and Christian living. While acknowledging the role of the Holy Spirit, reason, and experience, *sola scriptura* insists that these sources remain subordinate to scripture.³⁸ This principle guards against the elevation of subjective experience or ecclesiastical authority to a level that compromises biblical revelation.

In Pentecostal contexts where spiritual experiences are central, *sola scriptura* provides a critical theological anchor by ensuring that all claims to divine revelation are tested against the canonical witness of Scripture.³⁹ This preserves doctrinal coherence and continuity with the historic Christian faith.

Furthermore, *sola scriptura* also reinforces Christological and soteriological clarity by grounding teachings about Christ, salvation, and redemption firmly in Scripture. The Reformers viewed

³⁶ Ruth Marshall, *Political Spiritualities*, 44- 50

³⁷ Alister E McGrath, *Reformation Thought*, 44- 50

³⁸ Alister E. McGrath, *Christian Theology: An Introduction*, 6th ed. (Oxford: Wiley- Blackwell, 2017), 92 - 95

³⁹ Allan Anderson, *An Introduction to Pentecostalism*, 224 - 230

Scripture as the primary means through which Christ is known and proclaimed.⁴⁰ Theologically, this prevents doctrinal distortions that may arise when revelatory claims or charismatic authority figures redefine core Christian beliefs.

For Nigerian Pentecostal theology, this implication is particularly significant in maintaining biblical balance in teachings on prosperity, healing, and deliverance. Scripture serves as a corrective lens through which Christ-centered theology is preserved.

Another major theological implication of *Sola Scriptura* concerns the nature of Church authority. The doctrine relativizes ecclesiastical structures by subjecting all Church leaders, institutions, and traditions to the authority of Scripture.⁴¹ This undermines authoritarianism and reinforces the accountability of leaders to the biblical text and the believing community.

1.8.2 Ethical Implications of *Sola Scriptura*

Ethically, *sola scriptura* establishes Scripture as the primary source of moral guidance for Christian life. Ethical norms concerning holiness, justice, integrity, and compassion are derived from biblical teachings rather than cultural pragmatism or personal preference.⁴² This provides a stable moral framework in rapidly changing social contexts. In Nigeria, where Christians navigate complex ethical challenges such as corruption, poverty, and political instability, *sola scriptura* offers a scripturally grounded ethic that resists moral relativism.

Furthermore, one of the most significant ethical implications of *sola scriptura* is its capacity to sustain prophetic critique. The biblical tradition, especially the prophetic literature, emphasizes justice, accountability, and concern for the marginalized.⁴³ Through the scripture, Churches are empowered to challenge social injustices and unethical practices both within and outside ecclesial structures. This implication resonates strongly with African theological emphases on communal responsibility and social transformation.

Sola Scriptura also functions as an ethical safeguard against spiritual manipulation and abuse by insisting that all spiritual claims be evaluated in light of the scripture. The doctrine limits the potential misuse of prophetic authority and charismatic power.⁴⁴ Ethical accountability is therefore, embedded within the theological framework of *sola scriptura*.

⁴⁰ Martin Luther, *Luther's Works*, vol. 26 (St. Louis: Concordia, 1963), 58- 60

⁴¹ John Calvin, *Institutes of the Christian Religion*, 4- 9

⁴² Richard B. Hays, *The Moral vision of the New Testament* (San Francisco: Harper Collins, 1996), 3- 7.

⁴³ Walter Brueggemann, *The Prophetic Imagination*, 2nd ed. (Minneapolis Fortress Press, 2001), 13- 18.

⁴⁴ Kenneth J. Archer, *A Pentecostal Hermeneutics for the Twenty-first Century*, (London: T&T Clark, 2004), 211- 215

This is particularly significant in situations where unquestioned obedience to spiritual leaders has sometimes led to exploitation or coercion. Scripture becomes a protective norm for vulnerable believers.

Theologically and ethically, *sola scriptura* serves as a unifying principle that binds faith, doctrine, and moral practice. It affirms God's self-disclosure in Scripture while fostering ethical responsibility, communal accountability, and prophetic engagement with society. For Nigerian Pentecostal theology, the challenge lies not in affirming *sola scriptura* verbally but in embodying it consistently in doctrinal formulation, ethical practice, and ecclesial governance.

Therefore, a renewed commitment to the scripture as the final authority for evaluating revelation, experience, and leadership is essential for the theological integrity and ethical credibility of contemporary Christianity.

Conclusion

This study has shown that Nigerian Pentecostal theology both affirms and also modifies *sola scriptura* in some ways. While continuity exists in its high view of scripture and rejection of ecclesiastical tradition, significant divergence sets in in its elevation of prophetic revelation and charismatic authority. In other words, while the scripture is affirmed as authoritative in principle, charismatic revelation and leadership often exercise parallel authority in practice. These developments challenge classical Reformation formulations of *sola scriptura* and raise critical theological and ethical questions. Rather than rejecting Pentecostal experience, this article argues for a renewed commitment to *sola scriptura* as a critical and constructive principle that affirms the Spirit's work while anchoring faith and practice in the authoritative witness of the scripture. Such a reframing is essential for the theological integrity and prophetic credibility of Nigerian Pentecostal Christianity.

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